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Balangiga Aftermath

The valiant town in 1901,
It is Balangiga that stood for freedom.

People fleet with anguished outcry
From the deafening silence of post encounter.
In howling wilderness;
No more prisoners left.

Bodies of males above 10 are found lifeless,
Seized by bravery and freedom.

Its dreary river behind the old church,
Unhears the toll of bells drifting in town.
Burned nipa huts and grasses
The dark sky is bleeding with smoke.

A big ship left the coast,
Bringing the bells navigating the pacific,
Taken from the town by white looters.

The aftermath of ruins,
Lay blood-soaked and desolate.

Survivors from the mountains returned,
Seeing fallen Balangigan-ons.
Swallowed in woe.